

Protocol Description

We first need to lay out the actual protocol that we're talking about. Otherwise the proof doesn't make sense.

Protocol: LVI Requests

The protocol can access/manipulate storage in four places:

1. Acquiring/releasing locks goes to etcd
2. When the function executes in the datacenter, it may access/update application storage
3. Writing the status bit used for function idempotency
4. Reading from application storage to do the consistency check

Throughout the process, we track the status of the execution (probably want a better name for this). This status consists of:

1. The result of the consistency check
2. A status value: not started, on edge, started, and done

It is important to note that whenever we update the status, we use an expression that ensures status can never backtrack based on the following DAG:

When a request arrives at the datacenter for the very first time, we first check the status of the execution, using a test-and-set operation: if the status doesn't exist, we create a new one with value not started.

Then, we branch based on the value of the status.

Not Started

Locks may or may not be held

The very first thing that happens is the execution tries to get locks. Our lock service will give us the locks if this execution holds them, otherwise we'll have to wait.

Then we need to do is perform the consistency check. This works just like Radical non-replicated, with one change: before returning the result, we perform a test-and-set on the status that checks that the consistency check result in the stored status is null. If it isn't, we return that instead.

The update above also writes a new status value:

- on edge if the check succeeded
- started if it didn't

Proceed to the respective branches at this point

On Edge

Locks may or may not be held

On this branch, the following *must* be true:

- The consistency check succeeded

So, the first thing we do is setup write intents if necessary. This is also done using a test-and-set operation: if the write intents already exist, we don't touch them. *Write intents are bound to execution id.*

Then, we return to the edge.

Started

Locks may or may not be held

On this branch, the following *must* be true:

- The consistency check failed

The first thing we do is start running the function in the datacenter. When the function finishes, it collects all the updates it was going to make and writes them to storage in a transaction. This transaction only succeeds if the status for this execution is not done. If the status is done, no writes are applied.

Then, locks are released.

Then, we return to the edge.

Done

Locks may or may not be held

On this branch, one of the following *must* be true:

- The function ran to completion on the edge
- The function ran to completion in the datacenter, either as a timeout or due to a failed check

The only thing we do on this branch is release the locks: our lock service allows for double release.

Then we return to the edge.

Protocol: Followup/Timeout Requests

The protocol along this branch can manipulate storage in four places:

- The write intents, which are written in DynamoDB
- The locks
- The status for handling of the write intent
- The actual application storage when a is re-executed on a write intent timeout

We track the status of the write intent execution with a status item, just like the LVI protocol. The possible values for the status are:

- not started, started, and done

The status value follows the following DAG. Each time it will be updated, the update is wrapped in a conditional that prevents moving backwards along the graph.

This branch of the execution is kicked off when either:

1. A timer interrupt occurs
2. A followup arrives

Both must contain an execution ID that matches the execution ID for the corresponding instance of the read/write protocol

When a request arrives, it checks the current status, and sets one with a status of not started if it doesn't exist. This leaves four branches.

Not Started

Locks may or may not be held

Here, we need to branch on whether this was a timeout or not.

If yes: then we write the updates and set status to done in a single transaction. Then proceed to the Done branch.

If no: then we set status to started and proceed along that branch.

Started

Locks may or may not be held

This means that this occurred because of a timeout, and the function may or may not have been started.

Re-execute the function, which must wrap its updates in a transaction that checks for, and sets, the status to done.

Then proceed to the done branch.

Done

Locks may or may not be held

At this point, the intent must have been handled and all updates made to storage.

The only thing left is to release locks.

Proof

We make the above modifications to Radical's protocol. We seek to prove that, with these modifications—and with arbitrary failures of the server that handles the LVI protocol—Radical still provides Linearizability.

Linearizability is a local consistency model, so it is sufficient to show that operations on each individual key are linearizable. Without loss of generality, consider key k . All requests that modify k begin at the near-user location, and create an LVI request that contains k in the set of items to be validated. This LVI request also contains a unique execution identifier, eid , corresponding to that specific near-user request. This identifier is attached to any subsequent requests related to the execution made by the near-user location. Without loss of generality, we consider only a single execution identifier, eid .

We refer to the sequence of operations that take place in the near-primary storage location when handling the initial LVI request for eid as the LVI handler.

We refer to the sequence of operations that take place in the near-primary storage location when handling either the followup from the near-primary storage location *or* the potential timeout that occurs on the write intent set for eid as the *followup handler*.

Both the followup handler and the LVI handler may fail at any point during their execution. The near-user location will attempt to re-execute them on failure by sending a new request with the same eid to a live server, which begins handling the request from the beginning of the corresponding handler. Failures need not be fail-stop.

This means that there may be as many instances of the LVI and followup handlers as there are replicas of the server—locks are tied to key and execution id, so two handlers with the same execution id eid may proceed concurrently, while both hold the lock on k . This is intended behavior: otherwise a failed handler could deadlock the system. We refer to any subsequence of requests made during the execution of an LVI or followup handler as a partially executed handler.

The status values mentioned in the above protocol description are tied to eid . Each handler has a status value, which is stored in linearizable storage. At any given point in time, all currently executing handlers see the same status value as all the other executing handlers of the same type (LVI or followup).

Prior to proving Linearizability, we prove the following:

1. During the execution of either kind of handler for eid , no state can be modified without holding the lock on key k .
2. That any combination of partially executed handlers (either LVI or followup) produces a set of observable outputs that can also be produced by a single, fully completed execution of the same handler.

We then prove Linearizability by considering four pairs of operations, each captured by a single, complete execution of an LVI handler and followup handler, and show—by contradiction—that Radical maintains Linearizability in each case.

No modifications without locks

Modifications to state can only occur after locks have been acquired. However, a given handler h_1 may execute without locks because they are released by a second handler h_2 after it completes, but before h_1 does. Locks are released in three situations:

1. When the validate step of the LVI protocol fails, after the function runs to completion in the near-primary storage location
2. When the near-user location sends its followup to the near-primary storage location, after the near-primary storage location has applied all the updates contained in the followup to primary storage
3. When the timer on the write intent for eid expires, after the function has been deterministically re-executed in the near-primary storage location and its updates have been applied to primary storage

In all three of these cases, lock release is preceded by an update to primary storage that sets the status value for either the LVI handler. Above, we enumerated each point at which a handler may update storage. Each of these updates is conditional on the status value *not* being set to done. So, an update to storage without holding locks is impossible: updates cannot occur when the status is set to done, and if locks are not held, then the status must be set to done.

Dealing with partially executed handlers

When considering partial executions, we need only consider those that hold locks when they modify state. Any partial execution that does not hold a lock, cannot modify state as we proved above, which means it cannot impact linearizability: key k cannot be modified by that partial execution.

Now, we consider the set of possible updates made by n concurrent LVI handlers, and show that it is equivalent to the set of possible updates made by a *single*, complete LVI handler, where complete is defined by successfully returned back to the near-primary storage location. We consider LVI and followup handlers separately.

We only need to consider the updates made by the handlers as only updates can have an observable effect on other operations in the system.

LCD Handlers

Prior to performing the validate step of the LVI protocol, the LVI handler can make only one possible update: setting the status value to `not started`. This update is protected with a conditional that checks the current status, preventing more than one such update from being made. Only the first handler to successfully make the update in real-time order will be able to write to storage. The n handlers can make only one update collectively; this is equivalent to the set of updates a single, complete handler could make.

Then, we show that no two partial executions of an LVI handler can see a different result of the validate step of the LVI protocol. This is because the result of that step is included along with the status bit, and is only written to in an update that is conditional on there not being an existing result. If there is an existing result, that result will be returned instead. This means that only the first handler in real-time order to complete the update that marks the status as either `on edge` or `started` and stores the result of the validate step will be able to write that value. All executions will return the value written by that first one.

This means that either all the partial executions will proceed down the branch of the protocol with a successful validate step, or all will proceed down the branch with an unsuccessful validate step.

Successful Validate Step When the validate step succeeds, the LVI handlers will attempt two more updates to storage: setting the write intent, and setting status to done. The former can only occur once: write intents are created with a test-and-set operation. If one already exists, no write will occur.

The latter can also occur only once: updates can only reach primary storage if the status value is not done. So, only the first partially executed handler in real-time order to attempt to set the status value to done will do so. All the rest will make no writes that step.

Combined, this means that if the validate step succeeds, only one update can be made to set the write intent, and only one to update the status value. Clearly, this is identical to a single, complete execution of the LVI handler.

Unsuccessful Validate Step When the validate step fails, the LVI handlers will attempt three more updates to storage: writing the results of the backup function's execution, setting status to done, and releasing locks.

Only one request can write the results of the backup function's execution to storage: again, this is because writes are conditional on status not being done. *eid* is handed to the function as an argument, and it batches all of its updates into a single transaction after it is finished execution, which checks the status value for *eid* and sets it to done if the transaction succeeds. Because transactions are atomic, it is impossible to write the results and not set status to done. This ensures that only one partial execution can write the results of the backup function's execution.

The write to set status to done occurs as part of the function execution. As explained above, this can only occur once.

Releasing locks can only occur once as well. This is because locks can only be acquired once for a given *eid*, and the lock service prevents a handler for *eid* from releasing the locks if it does not hold them. So, once a locks have been released once, no further releases will be allowed to update the lock storage by the lock service.

Combined, the above three cases mean that if the validate step does not succeed, then only one update can be made for the backup function writes, the status value, and the lock release. Clearly, this is identical to a single, complete execution of the LVI handler.

Combining the Results Above, we show that:

1. Prior to executing the validate step, n partial LVI handlers will make a set of updates equivalent to a single, complete handler
2. n partial LVI handlers always see the same result of the validate step
3. After the validate step, the n partial LVI handlers will make a set of updates equivalent to a single, complete handler

These can be combined to show that the set of possible updates made by n partial LVI handlers is equivalent to the set of updates made by a single, complete LVI handler.

Followup Handlers

We now consider the followup handlers. Followup handlers may be triggered by either a timeout or a followup—we consider both at the same time, as they may occur concurrently.

The followup handler may make the following updates:

1. Setting the status value to `not started`, `started`, or `done`
2. Writing the results of deterministic re-execution to primary storage
3. Writing the results contained in a followup to primary storage
4. Releasing locks

First, we show that (2) and (3) are mutually exclusive and that only one of either can occur for n partial followup handlers. This is because both updates set the status value to done in a transaction with their other updates. This transaction is conditional on the status value not already being done. So, because transactions are atomic, only one can complete. This means that with n partial followup handlers, only update from (2) and (3) can occur. This is the same as if there were a single, complete followup handler.

For (1), all updates to the status are conditional on the status value not being the same or further along in the DAG laid out in the protocol description. Each transaction contains a conditional that prevents the transaction from

completing if this is not the case. This ensures that only one update to each status value can be made—the same as for a single, complete followup handler.

Releasing locks can only occur once for the same reasons as in the LVI handler.

In conjunction with the proof regarding concurrent, partial LVI handlers, the above show that the set of possible updates made by n partial LVI and followup handlers is equivalent to the set of possible updates made by a single, complete execution of an LVI and followup handler. For the remainder of the proof, we need only consider a single one of each.

Linearizability

Linearizability is a local consistency model. Thus, to prove that Radical is Linearizable, it is sufficient to show that operations on each individual key are linearizable. Radical supports two operations on key k : read ($r(k_v)$) and write ($w(k_v)$). These denote that key k was read or written to with version number v . Linearizability requires that there exists a total order of operations on k which we construct as follows:

For a given operation on key k op_i , we define $op_i.inv$ as the invocation time of that operation, and $op_i.resp$ as the time that operation returns its response.

1. Each write is ordered by its version number: $w(k_v) \xrightarrow{exe} w(k_{v+i}), i > 0$
2. Each read is ordered after the write that it observes: $w(k_v) \xrightarrow{exe} r(k_v)$
3. All reads that observe the same write are ordered by invocation time: $r_1(k_v) \xrightarrow{exe} \dots \xrightarrow{exe} r_n(k_v)$ if $r_1.inv < \dots < r_n.inv$

The total order must also obey real-time ordering constraints.

Proof Outline

To show that Radical is Linearizable, we show that Radical respects the above-constructed total order under real-time constraints. First, let all operations be illustrated as a directed graph where the operations are nodes that are connected by real-time edges. Then, there exists a total real-time order iff the directed graph is acyclic, meaning that the following invariant holds:

$$\forall op_i, op_j, \left(op_i \xrightarrow{rto} op_j \right) \implies \neg \left(op_j \xrightarrow{rto} op_i \right).$$

There exists a real-time edge between two operations op_1 and op_2 if op_2 sees the results of op_1 and starts after op_1 ends ($op_1.resp < op_2.inv$). This implies that ordering operations by real-time ordering is transitive.

Two operations have a real-time edge in one of two cases:

1. op_1 and op_2 are performed sequentially by the same function execution where op_1 precedes op_2 .
2. op_1 and op_2 are performed by two different executions and op_2 sees the results of op_1 via Radical's design.

We prove that Radical's total order is a real-time order by contradiction. More specifically, we consider pairs of operations (w, w) , (r, r) , (r, w) , and (w, r) where w are writes and r are reads.

As shown above, each r and w can be considered as a single, complete execution of Radical's protocol that holds the lock on k for its duration.

Case 1: Write, Write

Let there be two writes such that $w_1 = w(k_v) \xrightarrow{exe} w_2 = w(k_{v'}), v' > v$. We assume that $w_2 \xrightarrow{rto} w_1$. Because w_2 is real-time ordered before another operation, we know that w_2 must have completed, either at the near-user or near-primary storage location.

w_2 completed in the near-user location. It must have acquired a write lock as part of the LVI protocol. As it completed, its updates must have reached the near-primary storage location: either via followup or timeout. w_1

executed either: in the near-user location, in the near-primary storage location as part of a validation failure, or in the near-primary storage location as part of a timeout.

If w_1 runs in the near-user location, then it must have acquired a write lock on k as part of the LVI protocol. $w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} w_1 \implies w_2.\text{write_lock} < w_2.\text{resp} < w_1.\text{inv} < w_1.\text{write_lock}$. This means that w_1 must acquire the lock on k *after* w_2 releases it. Version numbers only increase on subsequent writs, so $v' < v$. This contradicts our assumption above.

If w_1 runs in the near-primary storage location due to validation failure, then it acquired a write lock on k prior to performing the validate step and could not run in the near-primary storage location before doing so. This creates the same contradiction as the previous case.

If w_1 runs in the near-primary storage location as part of a timeout on a write intent, then it must have succeeded the validate step and must, therefore, hold the write lock on k . On validation success, locks are not released until *after* the updates are reconstructed in the near-primary storage location. This creates the same contradiction as in the previous two cases— w_1 's updates must have a higher version number than w_2 's or it would not have been able to acquire the lock on k .

w_2 completed in the near-primary storage location. To complete in the near-primary storage location, w_2 must acquire a write lock on k prior to validation, and the validation must fail. The lock is released after w_2 completes executing in the datacenter. No other operation can modify k until w_2 completes in the near-primary storage location. w_1 has the same execution options as above.

If w_1 runs in the near-user location, it must have acquired the write lock on k during the LVI protocol. It cannot update k without releasing that lock. This necessitates that w_2 released the lock first. So, $w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} w_1 \implies w_2.\text{write_lock} < w_2.\text{resp} < w_1.\text{inv} < w_1.\text{write_lock} \implies v' < v$. Contradiction.

If w_1 runs in the near-primary storage location we create the same contradiction, as w_1 must acquire the write lock on k before performing the validation check which precedes executing in the near-primary storage location.

If w_1 runs in the near-primary storage location as part of a timeout, then it must still be holding the lock on k from LVI protocol. The lock is not released until *after* the timeout execution completes. This creates the same contradiction as the previous two cases.

Case 2: Read, Read

Let there be two reads such that $r_1 = r(k_v) \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} r_2 = r(k_{v'})$ where $v' > v$. We assume that $r_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r_1$. Because r_2 is real-time ordered before another operation, we know that r_2 must have completed. There are two cases.

First, the two reads return the same values. Then the two reads are ordered by invocation time. Since $r_1.\text{inv} < r_2.\text{inv}$, there cannot be a real-time edge from r_2 to r_1 . This is a contradiction.

If they read different values, then there must be a w_1 ordered before r_1 , as otherwise r_1 would have not had anything to read. Additionally, there must be a w_2 between r_1 and r_2 —otherwise the two reads would have read the same value. So, $w_1 \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} r_1, w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} r_2$.

We also know that there cannot be any writes to k between $r_1.\text{inv}$ and $r_1.\text{resp}$, or any writes between $r_2.\text{inv}$ and $r_2.\text{inv}$ because reads acquire a read lock prior to executing and only release it after responding.

If r_2 completes in the near-user location, then it must be the case that the validation step succeeded and the read lock on k was acquired. To have seen the write from w_1 , it must therefore be true that $w_1.\text{resp} < r_1.\text{inv} \implies w_1 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r_1$. The same logic applies to show that $w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r_2$. We also know, by assumption, that $r_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r_1 \implies w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} w_1 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r_1$ by transitivity. Writes are ordered in increasing version number; w_2 must have written v' and w_1 v . So, $v > v'$. This is a contradiction.

If r_2 completes in the near-primary storage location, then the read lock was acquired prior to a failed consistency check. This creates the same contradiction as above: no matter where r_1 executes, w_1 must have obtained the write lock on k prior to its execution, and the same for w_1 and w_2 , which in turn implies that $w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} w_1 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r_1$.

Case 3: Read, Write

Let there be a read and a write such that $r = r(k_v) \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} w_1 = w(k_{v'})$, $v' > v$. We also assume that $w_1 \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r$. Because w_1 is real-time ordered before another operation, we know that w_1 must have completed. There are two cases, as w_1 completes either in the near-user location or near-primary storage location.

If w_1 completes in the near-user location then it must have acquired and released the write lock on k before r executed—otherwise w_1 would not be real-time ordered before r . Additionally, for r to return v and not v' , there must be a second write $w_2 = w(k_v)$ ordered between the two. This creates a contradiction, as $w_1 \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} w_2 \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} r$ and $v' > v$: writes are ordered by increasing version number, which implies $v' < v$.

If w_1 completes in the near-primary storage location, then it must have acquired and released the write lock on k as part of execution after the failed validation step. By the same logic as above, there must still exist a w_2 between w_1 and r for r to see a different version number. This w_2 must execute after w_1 released the lock, creating the same out-of-order write contradiction as above.

Case 4: Write, Read

Let there be a write and a read that observes that write such that $w = w(k_v) \xrightarrow{\text{exe}} r = r(k_v)$. We also assume that $r \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} w$. Because r is real-time ordered before another operation, it must have completed. This means that there must have been *some* data for r to read—otherwise it would not have completed. There are two cases.

If r completes in the near-user location then it must have acquired the read lock on k as part of the LVI protocol. w must hold the write lock on k regardless of where it executes. It only releases this lock after all its updates have been applied to primary storage, either by executing directly near-primary storage location or via a followup from a near-user location. For r to have read v , then $w.\text{inv} < w.\text{write_lock} < w.\text{resp} < r.\text{inv} < r.\text{read_lock} \implies w.\text{resp} < r.\text{inv} \implies w \xrightarrow{\text{rto}} r$. This contradicts our assumption.

If r completes in the near-primary storage location, then it must have acquired the read lock prior to executing. Again, for r to have read version number v , the contradiction as the previous case arises.

Conclusion

Thus, as the ordering of all pairs of (w, w) , (r, r) , (r, w) , and (w, r) operations obeys the real-time order for key k , all sequences of operations on key k must obey the real-time order. This proves Linearizability.